

HISTORICAL AND SPIRITUAL HERITAGE, AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF THE FORMATION OF AESTHETIC CULTURE IN YOUTH

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Abstract. The article considers the rich historical material and spiritual heritage of Uzbekistan as an important factor in the formation of aesthetic culture among young people. The legal basis of the historical material and spiritual heritage and the process of its improvement are analyzed. An opinion was expressed about the rich material and spiritual heritage of Uzbekistan and the essence of the policy being conducted in relation to it. The role and importance of material and spiritual heritage and aesthetic values in the education of young people were considered.

Keywords: Rich historical material and spiritual heritage, aesthetic culture, aesthetic values, role of aesthetic culture and aesthetic values in youth education.

The establishment of a democratic legal state and civil society in Uzbekistan, rapid development in all spheres of social life, and the success of reforms depend on the social activity of young people and the level of individual knowledge. Today, increasing the social activity of young people, raising their spirituality, acquiring worldly knowledge by them, forming the skills of effective use of advanced technologies, and developing their aesthetic consciousness and culture is a matter of urgent importance. The social activity of young people is their pursuit of high noble goals, strong will, tireless work, formation as a physically and spiritually perfect human being, restoration of historical memory in them based on historical material and spiritual heritage, decision to realize national identity. based on finding.

The issue of preserving the historical material and spiritual heritage and passing it on to the next generations has a legal basis in Uzbekistan, in Article 61 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "Citizens have the right to the historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and must preserve its natural heritage. Historical, spiritual, cultural, scientific and natural heritage is protected by the state.

Today, attention is being paid to the restoration and deep study of Uzbekistan's rich historical material and spiritual heritage, national values. Further development of national culture of Uzbekistan, realization of national identity based on study of material and spiritual heritage, restoration of historical memory, awakening and strengthening of feelings of national pride and pride are ideological and ideological activities carried out in our country. is the main task of work. To do this, increase the spiritual and educational level and knowledge of our people, preserve and popularize

material and spiritual cultural heritage objects, actively integrate national culture into world material and spiritual culture, culture and art. A lot of attention is being paid to the implementation of complex measures such as strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, supporting representatives of the cultural sector.

Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society", "On approval of the concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On measures to fundamentally improve activities in the field of protection of tangible cultural heritage objects", "On measures to improve the activities of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and further development of their culture, focusing on the formation of their worldview while relying on material and spiritual heritage.

Let's never forget one fact: we are a nation that has created a great history, a great state, a great culture, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - We are a great nation that never shies away from work, is not afraid of difficulties, values justice, is determined and ambitious. If we are all one body and soul, act unitedly and harmoniously, if we are honest and clean and work with good intentions, we are a nation capable of achieving any goals, in other words, creating a new page of our history.

The concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan is of great importance in the preservation of historical material and spiritual heritage in young people, in the formation of aesthetic consciousness and culture in them. to inculcate national and universal values in the minds of young people, to preserve ethnic cultural traditions, to widely introduce modern information and communication technologies in the field of culture, to organize and develop mutually effective international relations in the field of culture, to national culture as a structural and integral part of world culture view, ensuring the full functioning of cultural and art institutions, further strengthening their material and technical base, establishing public control over the preservation of cultural heritage objects is becoming important in the implementation of such tasks.

Therefore, to preserve and develop our incomparable spiritual wealth, classical art, rare examples of national creativity, and to pass it on to future generations, - says President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, - the world's leading scientists and artists, the state and public figures, it is a noble duty of people of all cultures.

In order to improve the effectiveness of legal regulation in the field of culture in Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Cultural Activities and Cultural Organizations" was adopted. The purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of cultural activities and cultural organizations. Until the adoption of this law, legal relations in the field of cultural activities were "On the export and import of cultural assets", "On museums" and "On the protection and use of cultural heritage objects". " was regulated by laws and numerous by-laws.

There are different definitions of aesthetic culture, one of them is aesthetic culture - the process of aesthetic activity of a person, the material and spiritual values created as a result of it, a social phenomenon that is an important factor in the formation and maturity of a person. Aesthetic culture is a concept that expresses the result of

striving to know not only the surrounding world, but also the social reality surrounding a person, and it expresses the self-awareness of an individual, a nation, and a society. It is said that aesthetic culture expresses the needs and interests of social units, their peculiarities, their place in world history, and their attitude towards various social systems.

In another definition, aesthetic culture represents a system of attitudes and values associated with the spiritual and emotional activity of a person. Aesthetic culture is a specialized part of society's culture, and its state can be explained in connection with the development of art and aesthetic relations. Aesthetic relations and the system of aesthetic values corresponding to it are the elements of aesthetic culture.

In social sciences, the set of material and spiritual wealth, such as practical experience, moral, scientific, intellectual, religious and spiritual views, national culture and creativity created by generations, is called cultural heritage. The Uzbek people are the people with the richest and most ancient cultural heritage in Central Asia, because their ancestors, for three thousand years, turned the most comfortable, fertile, prosperous and unsettled part of the region into one of the great centers of material and spiritual culture of humanity, and have left us tens of thousands as a legacy. centers of culture and spirituality, who left thousands of philosophical, literary, secular and scientific works. Revealing these riches, showing the true cultural and spiritual image of the Uzbek people before humanity is a component of restoring our cultural heritage, a necessary condition for introducing Uzbekistan to the world.

Today, it is not only the preservation of existing unique historical monuments and artifacts, but also the search for works of art created by the Uzbek people that are national treasures, and their return to Uzbekistan, the restoration of historical material and spiritual heritage, aesthetic values. are important policy issues in the field.

At the present time, the evaluation of culture in the whole world from the point of view of universal human values, regardless of its religious, national, regional aspects, is the fruit of a person's spiritual and spiritual search, a stage, a view of a person's self-awareness, striving for perfection. it is becoming a priority to consider them as a high social benefit that has arisen during the course of natural-historical development.

Spiritual heritage is a product of spiritual development, created by human intelligence, capable of leading the next generation towards good development, contributing to the growth of people's consciousness and worldview, and their efforts to learn and master the world. It is a concept that represents a set of ancient values that are passed from ancestors to generations, and spiritual heritage is a single person, a separate group, according to the significance of the experience of ancestors, the spiritual wealth they left behind in the practical activities and way of thinking of future generations. or may refer to representatives of a particular nationality. According to the fact that they are created in a certain national language, they reflect national cultural and spiritual traditions, views, they are related to a nation, according to the fact that they cover different nationalities living in a certain area, they are related to a society, a certain state authority acts It can also be characteristic of a state according to the time it was created, and a civilization according to its place in the history of mankind.

In Uzbekistan, on September 10-15, 2019, the first International Handicrafts Festival was held in the city of Koqan under the auspices of UNESCO. Many of the

world's festivals took place in the forums such as the International Gifting Art held in Termiz, the International Art of Status held in Shahrisabz, as well as "Silk and Spices" in Bukhara and "Atlas Bayram" in Margilon. representatives of culture and art from their countries, in particular, famous scientists and experts who spread fame with their scientific work and practical work in the field of handicrafts, participated.

Today, in Uzbekistan, it is important to deeply study the ancient and rich history, to activate scientific research in this direction, to educate the young generation based on national values and the priceless heritage of our ancestors, and to create a sense of patriotism and pride in the society. is receiving a lot of attention.

Uzbekistan has a rich spiritual heritage, 26 thousand volumes of manuscripts and about 40 thousand volumes of ancient lithographic books are stored in the fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Institute of Oriental Studies also has more than 5,000 original historical documents. In addition, there are microfilm and photocopy funds from books stored in foreign funds, and this huge spiritual heritage belongs to various fields of science - medicine, chemistry, mathematics, history, and Islamic sciences. Manuscript sources date from the 9th century to the 20th century and are written in Arabic, Persian, ancient Turkic and other Eastern languages.

In Uzbekistan, in 2016, 22.8 billion soums were allocated from the budget for the repair, restoration and conservation of cultural heritage objects, and in 2021, this indicator will be 73.5 billion soums (o' sish was 3.2 times). Also, in 2016, 10.3 billion soums were allocated for the production of motion pictures under the state order, and in 2021, their amount increased almost 8 times to 81.4 billion soums. Also, serious attention is being paid to the construction and repair of cultural objects, more than 160 billion soums were allocated from the state budget for these purposes only in 2020-2021, which, in turn, 34 made it possible to improve and strengthen the appearance and material and technical base of cultural centers, 6 theaters and 20 museums. Currently, there are 68 museums of various fields in the system of the Ministry of Culture in Uzbekistan, which are 21 museums of local history, 17 art museums, 14 memorial museums, 5 literary memorial museums, and 1 natural and scientific museum.

Today in Uzbekistan, it is important to create a comprehensive system for instilling the value of historical material and spiritual heritage into the minds of young people. It is appropriate to create literature for pre-school education, general education and higher education institutions that express the value of historical and cultural heritage, and to provide educational institutions with them. Preservation of historical material and spiritual heritage, development of aesthetic culture of young people is one of the issues that Uzbekistan is paying great attention to today.

REFERENCES USED

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. Toshkent, “O‘zbekiston”, 2023 yil.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Oliy Majlisga murojaatnomasi // Milliy tiklanishdan – milliy yuksalish sari. 4-jild, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston, 2020 yil.
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Folklor san’ati – insoniyatning bolalik qo‘shig‘i // Niyati ulug‘ xalqning ishi ham ulug‘, hayoti yorug‘ va kelajagi farovon bo‘ladi. 3-jild, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston, 2019 yil.

4. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023, December). OLIY O 'QUV YURLARIDA TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O 'RNI. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 391-393).
6. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023, December). TALABA YOSHLARNI O 'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO 'LLASH. In *INTERDISCIPLINE INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 15, pp. 389-390).
7. Sultanova, O., & Sadullayev, S. (2024). APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION OF STUDENTS. *Science and innovation*, 3(B2), 431-433.
8. Sulstonova, O. (2022). QISHLOQ YOSHLARINING IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY AHVOLI VA UNI YAXSHILASH YO'LLARI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(2), 127-130.
9. Rajabovna, S. O. (2023). THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN YOUTH EDUCATION. *Academia Science Repository*, 4(04), 85-89.
10. Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2019). Умумтаълим мактаб ўқувчиларида таянч компетенциялар асосида тадқиқотчилик кўникмаларини шакллантириш: пед. фан...(PhD) дисс.
11. Narzieva, N. (2017). Development of Education And Research Activity Profile Class Students on The Basis of Integrative And Personal Approach. *www. auris-verlag. de*.
12. Mustafakulovich, K. S., & Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). Effect of Aesthetic Categories on Human Spirituality. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(11), 501-503.
13. Kurbanovna, S. D., & Mustafakulovich, K. S. (2022). The Role of Aesthetic Culture in Educational Processes. *Open Access Repository*, 8(04), 208-210.
14. Vahabov, M. T., Jamolov, L. U., Turgunboev, O., & Suvonova, D. K. (2022). Key Issues of Development Strategy and Educational Propagation of the New Uzbekistan. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES*, 3(11), 101-109.
15. Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). GO'ZALIK VA ULUGVORLIK KATEGORIYALARINING IJTIMOIIY-FALSAFIY TAHLILI. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 3(10), 96-98.
16. Suvanova, D. (2023). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE SIGNIFICANCE OF RELIGIOUS VALUES IN THE FORMATION OF AESTHETIC CULTURE AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(1 Part 1), 108-115.
17. Суванова, Д. К. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ У МОЛОДЕЖИ. In *История, современное состояние и перспективы инновационного развития науки* (pp. 86-88).
18. Суванова, Д. К. (2020). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ИСТОРИЧЕСКОГО СОЗНАНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ. In *Научные исследования: проблемы и перспективы* (pp. 206-210).

19. Suvanova, D., & Karoboyev, S. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF RELIGIOUS VALUES IN FORMING AESTHETIC CULTURE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(26), 103-108.
20. Kurbanovna, S. D. (2023). YOSHLARDA ESTETIK MADANIYAT SHAKLLANISHINING METODOLOGIK MASALALARI. *FINLAND" MODERN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS"*, 14(1).
21. Narzieva, N. N. (2019). Formation of research skills in general education school students based on basic competencies: ped. science...(PhD) diss. *Samarkand: SamDU*.
22. Norkuzievna, N. N., & Solievna, S. G. (2022). Formation of Students' Research Skills in the Process of English Lessons. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8, 141-143.
23. Norkuzievna, N. N., & Solievna, S. G. (2022, March). DEVELOPING RESEARCH SKILLS ON THE BASIS OF COMPETENT APPROACH TO STUDENTS IN AN INTEGRATED LEARNING CONDITION. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 151-154).
24. Norkuzievna, N. N. (2022). Development Of Research Competences Of Future Veterinary Specialists In The Process Of Lessons. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 15, 41-43.
25. Turgunboev, A., & Narzieva, N. N. (2022). Zoroastrianism's source of education-interpretation of veterinary and animal husbandry in" Avesta. *Scientific Journal of Agrobiotechnology and Veterinary Medicine*, ps, 1180-1183.
26. Hasanovna, S. K., & Nargiza, N. (2019). The advantages of teaching grammar through games. *Достижения науки и образования*, (6 (47)), 30-31.
27. Khusenova, N. I., Fayzieva, F. N., Narzieva, N. N., & Rajabova, G. R. (2019). THE CONTENT OF TEACHING LISTENING IN ENGLISH AT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL. In *EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY* (pp. 45-47).
28. Нарзиева, Н. (2017). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ У УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИНТЕГРАТИВНОГО ПОДХОДА. In *WORLD SCIENCE: PROBLEMS AND INNOVATIONS* (pp. 156-158).
29. Narzieva, N. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH COMPETENCIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF INTEGRATED EDUCATION IN STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF A COMPETENT APPROACH. *Thematics Journal of Education*, 8(Q1).
30. Narzieva, N. N. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RESEARCH COMPETENCES OF VETERINARY SPECIALISTS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF VETERINARY EDUCATION. *International Journal of Engineering Mathematics (Online)*, 5(3).
31. Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2022). СПОРТ ТУРЛАРИ БЎЙИЧА ТРЕНЕР-ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-МАДАНИЙ КОМПЕТЕНТЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 980-983.
32. Тургунбоев, А., & Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2022). ЗАРДЎШТИЙЛИКНИНГ ТАЪЛИМ-ТАРБИЯ МАНБАИ-“АВЕСТО” ДАГИ ВЕТЕРИНАРИЯ ВА ЧОРВАЧИЛИК ТАЛҚИНИ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 1180-1183.

33. Narzieva, N., Namazova, U., & Ernazarov, T. (2022). FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE OF HISTORY TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (5), 171-173.
34. Рахимов, Б. Х., & Нарзиева, Н. Н. (2016). ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПОДХОДА К ОБУЧЕНИЮ. In *Образование через всю жизнь: непрерывное образование в интересах устойчивого развития* (pp. 356-360).
35. Назарова, Б., Нарзиева, Н., Умаров, Х., Машарипов, К., & Кулахметова, М. (2011). ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ПРОЦЕСС ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НАУЧНОГО МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ. *Педагогические науки*, (1), 147-151.
36. Нарзиева, Н. Н., & Гаппарович, Ҳ. А. ТАЯНЧ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ИЗЛАНИШ, ТАДҚИҚОТ МАДАНИЯТИНИ БОСҚИЧМА-БОСҚИЧ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ. *НАМАНГАН ДАВЛАТ УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ-2021*, 1, 528.
37. Davlatov, R. B., & Khushnazarov, A. K. (2024). Diagnosis and chemoprophylaxis of rabbit eumeriosis. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 480, p. 03020). EDP Sciences.
38. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., & Эшкораев, А. (2023). Способы кормления кроликов в современных клетках. *in Library*, 1(1), 52-57.
39. Эшкораев, А., Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Развитие, эпизоотология, лечение и профилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 65-71.
40. Раимкулов, И., Хушназаров, А., Эшкораев, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Химиопрофилактика эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(1), 56-62.
41. Расулов, У., Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Диагностика и эпизоотология эмериоза кроликов. *in Library*, 1(2), 366-368.
42. Газнакулов, Т. К., Орипов, А. О., Сафаров, А. А., Хушназаров, А. Х., Давлатов, Р. Б., Абдухакимов, Ш., ... & Мавланов, С. (2023). ХС Салимов, МК Бутаев, ЗЭ Рузиев, –Биохавфсизлик.
43. Хушназаров, А. Х., Райимкулов, И. Х., Эшқораев, А. М., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). Қуён эймериозининг кимёпрофилактикаси. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
44. Khushnazarov, A. K., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DIAGNOSTICS OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 72-77.
45. Ergashov, S. I., Xushnazarov, A. X., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). QUYONLAR EYMERIOZNI DAVOLASHDA KENG QO‘LLANILADIGAN PREPARATLAR. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 58-64.
46. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Қуён эймериозининг тарқалиши ва патологоанатомик ташҳиси. *Library*, 1(1), 15-17.
47. Мухаммадиев, У. И., Хушназаров, А. Х., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). BIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RABBITS. KEEPING AND FEEDING TECHNOLOGY.
48. Khushnazarov, A. K., Eshkorayev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT, EPISOTOLOGY, TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF EMERIOSIS IN RABBITS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 65-71.

49. Хушназаров, А., Эшкораев, А., Ахмадалиев, Т., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Эпизоотологические диагностические и профилактические данные эймериоз кроликов. in *Library*, 1(1), 1068-1080.
50. Ахмадалиев, Н. Т., Хушназаров, А. Х., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРОЗИНИНГ ЭПИЗООТОЛОГИЯСИ.
51. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Распространение и патологоанатомическая диагностика эмериоза кроликов. in *Library*, 1(1), 15-17.
52. Akhmadaliev, N. T., Khushnazarov, A. K., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). EPIZOOTOLOGY OF RABBIT EYMEROSIS.
53. Ergashov, S. I., Khushnazarov, A. X., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DRUGS WIDELY USED IN THE TREATMENT OF EMERIOSIS IN RABBITS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(3), 58-64.
54. Хушназаров, А. Х., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). HISTORY AND SYSTEMATIC STATUS OF THE STUDY OF RABBIT EYMEROSIS.
55. Khushnazarov, A. H., Rayimkulov, I. H., Eshkoraev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). СЕМИОПРОФИЛАКСИС ОФ ЭМЕРИОЗИНИНГ ИН РАББИТ. *SCHOLAR*, 1(2), 56-62.
56. Мухаммадиев, У. И., Хушназарова, М. И., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). DIAGNOSTICS AND PROPHYLAXIS OF RABBIT PASTEURELLIOS (LITERATURE ANALYSIS).
57. Хушназаров, А., Райимкулов, И., & Эшқораев, А. (2023). ЗАМОНАВИЙ КАТАКЛАРДА ҚУЁНЛАРНИ БОҚИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.
58. Хушназаров, А. Х., Хушназарова, М. И., & Исоқулова, З. Х. (2023). Эймериоцид препаратларни қуён эймериозиди қўллаш. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(1), 138-143.
59. Khushnazarov, A., Rayimkulov, I., & Eshkoraev, A. (2023). METHODS OF KEEPING RABBITS IN MODERN CAGES. *Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences*, 3(1 Part 2), 52-57.
60. Khushnazarov, A. K., Khushnazarova, M. I., & Isokulova, Z. K. (2023). EIMERIOCID DRUGS KUYONG EIMERIOSYS KOLLASH. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(1), 138-143.
61. Газнакулов, Т. К., Орипов, А. О., Сафаров, А. А., Хушназаров, А. Х., Давлатов, Р. Б., & Абдухакимов, Ш. & Мавланов, С. (2023). *ХС Салимов, МК Бутаев, ЗЭ Рузиев, –Биохавфсизлик*.
62. Khudoyberdievich, K. A., Khushnazarova, M. I., & Isokulova, Z. X. (2022). PREVALENCE, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(9), 245-249.
63. Давлатов, Р. Б., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2022). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРОЗИ ЭПИЗООТОЛОГИЯСИ ДАВОЛАШ ВА ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИ. *AGROBIOTEKNOLOGIYA VA VETERINARIYA TIBBIYOTI ILMIY JURNALI*, 181-184.
64. Berdiyevich, D. R., Khudoyberdi o'g'li, K. A., & Ilhomovna, K. M. (2022). EPIZOOTOLOGY OF EIMERIOSIS (COCCIDIOSIS) OF RABBITS, TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES. *Ann. For. Res*, 65(1), 602-607.

65. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2022). Quyon eumeriozini davolashda vazuril preparatining samaradorligi. *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.
66. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Пастдаргом ва ургут туманларида қуён эймериозининг эпизоотик ҳолати. *Library*, 22(1), 31-32.
67. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Қуён эймериозини даволашда янги эймериостатикнинг самарадорлиги. *Library*, 22(1), 28-29.
68. Давлатов, Р., & Хушназаров, А. (2022). Epizootology of eimeriosis (coccidiosis) of rabbits, treatment and preventive measures. *Library*, 22(4), 15.
69. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2022). Эффективность вазурила при лечении эймериоза кролика. in *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.
70. Davlatov, R. B., & Khushnazarov, A. X. (2022). TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF THE EPISOTOLOGY OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF AGROBIOTECHNOLOGY AND VETERINARY MEDICINE, 181-184.
71. Давлатов, Р., & Хушназаров, А. (2022). Эпизотология эймериоза (кокцидоза) кроликов, лечение и профилактика. in *Library*, 22(4).
72. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Эпизототическая ситуация по эмериозу кролика в пастдаргомском и ургутском районах. in *Library*, 22(1), 31-32.
73. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2022). Эффективность нового эмериостатического препарата в лечении эймериоза кроликов. in *Library*, 22(1), 28-29.
74. Khushnazarov, A., & Davlatov, R. B. (2022). Rabbit eimeriozin in treatment vazuril of the drug efficiency. *Library*, 22(2), 173-174.
75. Хушназаров, А. Х. (2022). ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫХ ДАННЫХ ПО ХИМИОТЕРАПИИ И ХИМИОПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ЭЙМЕРИОЗА КРОЛИКОВ. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 23(2), 83-86.
76. Худойбердиевич, Х. А., Хушназарова, М. И., & Исоқулова, З. Х. (2022). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРИОЗИНИНГ ТАРҚАЛИШИ, ДИАГНОЗИ, ДАВОЛАШ ВА ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШ. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(9), 245-249.
77. Хушназаров, А., Хабибулаев, С. Л., Рахматова, У., Орлова, Г. И., Толибова, Ф. Т., & Хушназарова, М. И. (2022). Защита кроликоферм от эймериоза. in *Library*, 22(2), 5-8.
78. Хушназаров, А., Хабибулаев, С. Л., Рахматова, У., Орлова, Г. И., Толибова, Ф. Т., & Хушназарова, М. И. (2022). Защита кроликоферм от эймериоза. in *Library*, 22(2), 5-8.
79. Khushnazarov, A. X. (2022). OBZOR LITERATURNYX DANNYX PO KHMIIOTERAPII I KHMIIOPROPHYLAKTIKI EUMEROZA KROLIKOV. *Journal of PEDAGOGS*, 23(2), 83-86.
80. Урокова, М., Акрамова, М., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2021). Эффективные методы лечения эмериоза у кроликов. in *Library*, 21(2), 115-117.